

Interaction between DL-threonine and ninhydrin in aqueous, aqueous-organic and micellar media^ψ

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The kinetics of formation of the *Ruhemann's purple* by the reaction of DL-threonine and ninhydrin has been investigated in aqueous, aqueous-organic and cationic micelles of CTAB (solvents used : acetonitrile, 1-propanol, methyl cellosolve and dimethyl sulfoxide). The order of the reaction with respect to threonine is unity while it is fractional with respect to ninhydrin. On the basis of these studies, a mechanism has been proposed. Also, the results obtained in the micellar medium are treated quantitatively in terms of the kinetic pseudo-phase model where the following rate equation is obeyed

$$k_{\psi} = \frac{k_w[N]_T + (K_A k_m - k_w) m_N^S [D_n]}{1 + K_A [D_n]}$$

CTAB micelles decrease the activation enthalpy and make the activation entropy less negative, which shows formation of a well-structured activated complex.

Ninhydrin is an important analytical reagent. The science of fingerprints is largely indebted to the use of ninhydrin for the detection and estimation of amino acids¹ which help in the formation of diketohydrindylidenediketohydrindamine (DYDA)^{2,3}, popularly known as *Ruhemann's purple* (RP). Although breakthroughs were made in understanding the reactions of ninhydrin with amino functionality, there are still questions that await answers. Consequently, there have been persistent efforts to make this reaction more efficient and cost effective²⁻⁴.

The rate of formation of *Ruhemann's purple* is influenced by surfactant micelles^{5,6}. Micelles are known to provide different microenvironment for different parts of the reactant molecules as there is a non-polar, hydrophobic interior that can provide binding energy for similar groups and polar, usually charged, palisade layer that can interact with reactants polar parts. These properties of micelles play an important role in influencing the rates of reactions.

Threonine is an essential amino acid. It cannot be formed by transamination of the keto acid. It is glucogenic. The amino acid is a constituent of all proteins and, like serine, it can combine with phosphate in case of phosphoproteins (it acts as PO₄ carrier).

To understand the reaction process of threonine with

ninhydrin a systematic kinetic investigation has been made in absence and presence of cationic micelles both in aqueous and aqueous-organic media. The results are described in this paper.

Results

Spectra of the product : All spectra of the purple coloured product (formed by the reaction of threonine with ninhydrin) were noted after completion of the reaction in aqueous, aqueous-organic or micellar media. The spectra consist of peaks at $\lambda_{\max} = 400, 570$ nm for all media, which are in line with literature values⁵⁻⁹. The observation leads to the conclusion that the presence of CTAB and/or organic solvents did not bring any change in the product formation. It has been also observed that the reaction between ninhydrin and threonine is catalyzed in presence of different fixed CTAB concentrations, Fig. 1(A), and solvents, Fig. 1(B).

Effect of pH : The solution pH plays a pivotal role in the amino acid-ninhydrin reactions; this being the reason that the effect of pH on the rate of threonine-ninhydrin reaction was studied in the range 3.6 to 6.0. It was found that the rate constant increased upto pH 5.0 and thereafter became independent of pH (Fig. 2).

Effect of ninhydrin : In the absence and presence of

^ψDedicated to Professor Y. K. Gupta on his 80th birth anniversary.

Fig. 1(A). Absorption spectra of the reaction product of threonine with ninhydrin in absence of CTAB (a, b), $5.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ CTAB (c), $10.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ CTAB (d), $10.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ CTAB + 10% DMSO (e). Reaction conditions : [threonine]_T = $1.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ (a), $2.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ (b-e), [ninhydrin]_T = $5.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, pH = 5.0, temp. = 80°C.

Fig. 1(B). Absorption spectra of the reaction product of threonine with ninhydrin in absence of solvent (a, b), 10% dimethyl sulfoxide (c), 10% methyl cellosolve (d), 10% 1-propanol (e), 10% acetonitrile (f). Reaction conditions : [threonine]_T = $1.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ (a), $2.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ (b-f), [ninhydrin]_T = $5.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, pH = 5.0, temp. = 80°C.

CTAB, the dependence of rate constants was observed at different [ninhydrin] from $5.0\text{--}40.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ at constant [threonine] ($2.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$), [CTAB] ($20.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) (when required) and pH (5.0) at 80°C. The results are presented in Fig. 3. We see that the plots of k_{obs} and k_{ψ} vs [ninhydrin] are non-linear which resulted in linear log-log plots with slopes less than unity. This shows fractional order in [ninhydrin].

Effect of threonine : The k_{obs} and k_{ψ} were calculated at different initial threonine concentrations with a view to find the order with respect to threonine. The values of rate constants (Table 1) are independent of the initial concentration of threonine. The order of reaction in [threonine] is thus unity.

Effect of surfactant : The dependence of rate constant on [CTAB] was studied by undertaking a number of kinetic experiments at different surfactant concentrations. The results are shown graphically in Fig. 4.

Effect of temperature : A number of kinetic experiments were undertaken in the temperature range 70–90°C in the absence and presence of $20.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ CTAB (Table

Fig. 2. Effect of pH on the reaction rate of threonine with ninhydrin in absence of CTAB (a), and in presence of $2.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ CTAB (b). Reaction conditions : [threonine]_T = $2.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, [ninhydrin]_T = $5.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, temp. = 80°C.

Fig. 3. Effect of [ninhydrin] on the reaction rate of threonine with ninhydrin in absence of CTAB (a), and in presence of $2.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ CTAB (b). Reaction conditions : [threonine]_T = $2.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, pH = 5.0, temp. = 80°C.

1). Eyring equation was used to obtain enthalpies and entropies of activation.

Effect of solvents : The effect on the rate of purple colour formation by the addition of organic solvents, viz. methyl cellosolve (MCS), 1-propanol (C_3OH), dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) and acetonitrile (AN) was studied at constant [threonine] ($2.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$), [ninhydrin] ($5.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$), pH (5.0) and temperature (80°C). The results are presented graphically in Fig. 5. The effect of DMSO on the rate of reaction was observed in presence of CTAB ($20.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$), Fig. 6, also.

Discussion

Because of the use across a wide spectrum of disciplines, mechanistic and structural studies of ninhydrin reactions have attracted attention of scientists of different fields^{3,4}. It is well documented that α -amino acids on interaction with ninhydrin form purple-coloured diketohydrindylidene-diketohydrindamine (DYDA), popularly known as

Table 1. Dependence of the pseudo first-order rate constants (k_{obs} , k_{Ψ}) on [threonine] and temperature

[Ninhydrin]_T = $5.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, pH = 5.0, [CTAB]_T = $20.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$

10^4 [threonine] mol dm^{-3}	Temp. (°C)	$10^5 k_{\text{obs}}$ s^{-1}	$10^5 k_{\Psi}$ s^{-1}
2.0	80	7.8	17.4
2.5	—	7.2	17.3
3.0	—	7.9	17.0
3.5	—	7.0	17.4
4.0	—	7.2	17.6
2.0	70	3.6	9.5
	75	5.6	13.1
	80	7.8	17.4
	85	10.5	19.9
	90	15.1	27.5

Activation parameters :

E_a (kJ mol ⁻¹)	71.9	52.7
ΔH^\ddagger (kJ mol ⁻¹)	68.9	49.8
ΔS^\ddagger (JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)	-130.0	-178.0

Fig. 4. Effect of [CTAB] on the reaction rate of threonine with ninhydrin. Reaction conditions : [threonine]_T = $2.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, [ninhydrin]_T = $5.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, pH = 5.0, temp. = 80°C.

Ruhemann's purple (RP); the summarized mechanism is provided in Scheme 1. The condensation between the carbonyl group of ninhydrin and deprotonated amino group of amino acid takes place. The reaction starts through the attack of lone pair of electrons of amino nitrogen to the carbonyl group of ninhydrin to give a Schiff base (C, after decarboxylation) which is a characteristic of common addition-elimination reactions. This Schiff base is unstable and

Fig. 5. Effect of methyl cellosolve (a), 1-propanol (b), dimethyl sulfoxide (c), and acetonitrile (d) on the reaction rate of threonine with ninhydrin. Reaction conditions : $[\text{threonine}]_T = 2.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{ninhydrin}]_T = 5.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $\text{pH} = 5.0$, $\text{temp.} = 80^\circ\text{C}$.

hydrolyses to give 2-amino-indanedione (D1) and an aldehyde. 2-Amino-indanedione, in turn, reacts with another ninhydrin molecule to yield RP (route (a)). D1 gives ammonia (upon hydrolysis) and hydrindantin (route (b)). The yield of these products depends upon the reaction conditions (pH and temperature). At $\text{pH} < 5$, the reaction proceeds chiefly by route (b), where ammonia is evolved quantitatively and no purple colour is produced. In solutions of $\text{pH} > 5$, route (a) predominates and under these conditions, colour formation makes the basis of the analytical method. Hydrindantin, if formed, reduces the yield of RP. The 2-imino-indanedione (F), upon hydrolysis, gives ammonia which may react with hydrindantin to give RP (route (c)). The present studies were performed such that reactions of the alternate routes (b) and (c) were suppressed (almost completely) by carrying out experiments at elevated temperature ($\geq 70^\circ\text{C}$) and $\text{pH} = 5.0$ (formation of ammonia is negligible at $\text{pH} \geq 5$)^{10,11}.

Fig. 6. Effect of DMSO on the reaction rate of threonine with ninhydrin in presence of CTAB. Reaction conditions : $[\text{threonine}]_T = 2.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{ninhydrin}]_T = 5.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{CTAB}]_T = 2.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $\text{pH} = 5.0$, $\text{temp.} = 80^\circ\text{C}$.

As regards the reaction in aqueous medium, the amount of reaction products (carbon dioxide, aldehyde, ammonia, hydrindantin and RP) have been found to depend upon the conditions of reaction medium, i.e. pH, temperature, $[\text{ninhydrin}]$, etc.^{2,10}. It was also observed that the rate of evolution of CO_2 is fast in comparison to the rate of purple colour formation (at 80°C , evolution of CO_2 was completed within 20 min while the intensity of purple colour was negligible within this time interval¹⁰). This confirmed that the reaction of ninhydrin with α -amino acid has two steps. The mechanism of first step is the formation of a Schiff base (C) which has a double-bonded nitrogen atom and the decarboxylation is considered to take place through unionized acid, possibly via formation of an unionized chelated ring structure. The decarboxylation step is not the rate-determining because, under the experimental conditions ($\text{pH} 5.0$), it is expected to be unimolecular and not subjected to steric hindrance. The hydrolysis of C to 2-amino-indanedione (D1) could not be rate controlling as well because rates should be governed by steric factors alone¹². On the other hand, the reaction of D1 with ninhydrin also involves an addition-elimination type interaction leading to the formation of RP. The protonated amino group will decrease its nucleophilic character, while protonating the carbonyl group of ninhydrin will enhance the reaction. These two conditions are affected oppositely by pH and, there-

Scheme 1

fore, the maximum rate will be found at pH where not all of the $-\text{NH}_2$ group has been protonated and, at the same time, enough of the ninhydrin exists as its conjugate acid (keto form) to afford a reasonable reaction rate.

Under our experimental conditions, the zwitterionic form (Z) of the amino acid is the major existing species which is inactive towards nucleophilic attack on the carbonyl carbon of ninhydrin^{8,10} because the zwitterionic form

has a positive charge on the nitrogen atom (the unshared electron pair of nitrogen is not available). Therefore, the neutral form of amino acid (A), which exists in equilibrium with the zwitterionic form¹³, is the active species.

Now we take into account the kinetic data obtained in micellar systems. Fig. 4 shows that the observed pseudo first-order rate constant increases upon increasing the [CTAB] at low surfactant concentrations that reaches a maximum value at about $20.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$. The profile shape is perfectly general being a common characteristic of reactions catalyzed by micelles¹⁴⁻¹⁶.

The reaction rate in the presence of CTAB micelles may be discussed in terms of pseudo-phase model of the micelles developed by Menger and Portnoy¹⁴ and modified by Bunton^{15,17} and Vera and Rodenas¹⁸. Under the experimental conditions of this study the reaction scheme in the presence of CTAB micelles may be given as

Scheme 2

A is the amino acid whose binding constant to the micelle, K_A , is written in terms of micellized surfactant :

$$K_A = \frac{[A_m]}{[A_w][D_n]} \quad (1)$$

The pseudo first-order rate constants, k'_w and k'_m , in aqueous and micellar pseudo-phases are given by :

$$k'_w = k_w [N_w] \quad (2)$$

$$k'_m = k_m [N_m] / [D_n] = k_m m_N^S \quad (3)$$

where k_w and k_m are the second-order rate constants and m_N^S is the mole ratio of ninhydrin bound to the micellar head group. From Scheme 2, rate eq. (4) is derived :

$$k_\psi = \frac{k_w [N]_T + (K_A k_m - k_w) m_N^S [D_n]}{1 + K_A [D_n]} \quad (4)$$

Values of mole ratio $m_N^S (= [N_m]/[D_n])$ were estimated by considering the equilibrium

$$N_w + D_n \xrightleftharpoons{K_N} N_m$$

$$K_N = \frac{[N_m]}{[N_w]([D_n] - [N_m])} \quad (5)$$

and the mass balance for ninhydrin, i.e.

$$[N]_T = [N_w] + [N_m] \quad (6)$$

Upon solving eqs. (5) and (6), a quadratic eq. (7) results, which was solved for $[N_m]$ with the help of a computer program with K_N as an adjustable parameter. m_N^S was then calculated with the help of eq. (3).

$$K_N [N_m]^2 - (1 + K_N [D_n] + K_N [N]_T) [N_m] + K_N [D_n] [N]_T = 0 \quad (7)$$

In order to determine k_m and K_A kinetically we need the cmc under kinetic conditions which were determined conductimetrically (see Experimental). For a given value of cmc the k_m and K_A were calculated from eq. (4) using a non-linear least squares technique. Such calculations were carried out at different presumed values of K_N . The best fit values are : $k_w = 15.6 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$, $k_m = 5.6 \times 10^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$, $K_A = 82 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ dm}^3$, $K_N = 60 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ dm}^3$.

In order to confirm the Scheme 1 mechanism, effect of variables on the rate constants were seen in presence of constant [CTAB]. It was found that the reaction follows the same first- and fractional-order kinetics with respect to [amino acid] and [ninhydrin]. Thus, we can conclude that the reaction mechanism remains the same in presence of CTAB micelles as that in the aqueous medium with all possible intermediary situations. In the micellar medium the reaction of both A_w and A_m with N_w and N_m takes place. The enhancement of rate in presence of cationic micelles could then be attributed to the stabilization of intermediate C (i.e. the Schiff base) on the positively charged micellar surface, thereby increasing the concentration of the intermediate in the Stern layer. The presence of π -electrons in ninhydrin³ increases the possibility of its partitioning between water and positively charged micelles¹⁹. Therefore, both the reactants get effectively incorporated/associated into the aqueous surface of the micelles (i.e. the Stern layer – considered to be the usual sight of ionic micelle-mediated organic reactions¹⁷). Thus, the overall increase of reaction rate is due to concentrating both the reactants in the micellar reaction zone.

Effect of temperature : The effect of temperature on the CTAB-catalyzed reaction in presence of constant CTAB was used to evaluate activation parameters. Comparing the val-

ues with those obtained in aqueous medium (Table 1), we find that the presence of cationic micelles catalyzes the threonine-ninhydrin reaction and lowers the ΔH^\ddagger with more negative ΔS^\ddagger . This lowering may occur not only through the adsorption of both the reactants on the micellar surface but also through stabilization of the transition state². A meaningful mechanistic explanation of the apparent values of ΔH^\ddagger and ΔS^\ddagger is not possible because the k_ψ does not represent a single elementary kinetic step; it is a complex function of true rate, binding and ionization constants.

Effect of solvents : Addition of small amounts of water-soluble organic solvents increased the rate as well as intensity of the colour (Fig. 5). This unique behaviour of organic solvents towards the ninhydrin-amino acid reaction may be explained by the fact that as the solvent volume increases, the volume of water decreases in a given set of experiments, resulting in a decrease of the rate of hydrolysis (*cf.* Scheme 1)⁹. Thus, with the increasing organic solvent content, the side reaction is progressively blocked. Secondly, *Ruhemann's purple* is highly soluble in organic solvents^{7,10,20,21}, thereby imparting increased intensity. The synergistic effect (Fig. 6) of combined presence of DMSO and surfactant could be due to blockage of side reaction as well as preconcentration of reactants in a small volume of the micellar surface region.

Experimental

Cetyltrimethyl ammonium bromide (CTAB, Kochlight, England, 99%), ninhydrin (Merck, India, 99%), methyl cellosolve (SRL, India, 99%), dimethyl sulfoxide (Merck, India, 99%), 1-propanol (B.D.H., England, 99.5%), acetonitrile (Qualigens, 99%) and DL-threonine (B.D.H., England, 99%) were used as received. Doubly distilled water with specific conductivity ($1-2 \times 10^{-6}$ S cm⁻¹) was used throughout. Stock solutions of threonine and ninhydrin were prepared in CH₃COONa-CH₃COOH buffer solution²². ELICO pH-meter (LI-120, Hyderabad, India) in conjunction with glass-saturated calomel electrode LI-41 was used for pH measurements.

Kinetic procedure : A three-necked reaction vessel equipped with a double-surface water condenser was used to carry out the experiments. The vessel containing the required solutions of threonine, surfactant (when required) and solvent (when required) was immersed in an oil-bath maintained at the required temperature ($\pm 0.1^\circ\text{C}$). A stream of pure nitrogen gas (free from CO₂ and O₂) was bubbled through the reaction mixture for stirring as well as to maintain an inert atmosphere. The reaction was started by adding thermally equilibrated ninhydrin and the progress

of the reaction was monitored spectrophotometrically by measuring absorbance of the reaction product (purple coloured) at 570 nm using a Bausch and Lomb Spectronic-20. The ninhydrin concentration was maintained in excess in order to work under pseudo first-order conditions. The observed pseudo first-order rate constants in aqueous (k_{obs} , s⁻¹) and micellar (k_ψ , s⁻¹) media were obtained up to the completion of three half-lives by using a computer program^{5,6,9}.

Determination of cmc by conductivity measurement : The critical micelle concentration (CMC) values of surfactant solutions were determined conductimetrically. First, the conductivity of the solvent was measured and then small volumes of the stock solution of CTAB were added and the conductivity was recorded after each addition. The solvent correction was applied for determining the specific conductivity. The CMC values of the surfactant in the presence and absence of reactants were obtained from the break points of nearly two straight line portions of the specific conductivity vs concentration plots²³. Different conditions were maintained for carrying out experiments, i.e. solvent being water, water + threonine (2.0×10^{-4} mol dm⁻³), water + ninhydrin (5.0×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³) or water + threonine + ninhydrin – the respective values at 25 and 80°C are : 9.8, 16.4; 9.4, 15.4; 9.3, 15.8; 9.0, 15.6×10^{-4} mol dm⁻³.

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